

Post-Quantum Cryptographic Algorithm: A systematic review of round-2 candidates.

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Abstract— The rise of the new paradigm (Quantum computing) in the recent years have created a major security challenge to classical and widely used primitive cryptography schemes such as ECC (Elliptic Curve Cryptography) and RSA (Rivest-Shamir-Adleman) Algorithm. These classical computing algorithms depend on the problems of discrete logarithm and integer factorization respectively. Recent advancements in quantum computing have made encryption schemes more vulnerable since they are weak to some quantum attacks, like Shor's Algorithm and Grover's Algorithm. Therefore the call for a new set of algorithms known as Post-Quantum cryptography (PQC) that would not be vulnerable to quantum attacks is imminent. NIST have selected some candidates in the second round of Post-Quantum Cryptographic algorithms standardization project. This work's goal is to review these algorithms under these types. A rigorous survey on each Post-Quantum Cryptography schemes and their underlying properties will be x-rayed while recommending areas for research in this new security paradigm.

Keywords— *KEM, Cryptography, Digital Signature, Quantum Computer, Security*

I. INTRODUCTION

Cryptography is the science of hiding information meant for a recipient so that intruders cannot understand the message even when it is intercepted. Only the intended recipient can unravel the message using a key. Post Quantum cryptography is the application of existing cryptographic algorithms or the design of new algorithms that are quantum proof.

The computer system used in our daily computing activities uses the bit system: a "0" or a "1". In other words, Classical computers perform its operations using the binary position of the bit. This implies that very task carried out by our classical computers takes either of these two states. A single state such as on or off, up or down, 1 or 0 is called a bit. Qubit is what the quantum computer uses. They don't use the two-state position of 0s and 1s like the classical computers. Quantum computers

use a four-state superimposition to encode data. The four states of the quantum computer qubits are represented as ions, atoms, photons or electrons on devices for processing data. A quantum computer will probably be more powerful than even the most powerful supercomputer because of its ability to represent data in multiple states.. (Zentachain, 2019)

A lot of research has been on-going on quantum computers (machines that will use quantum phenomena to bring solutions to hard mathematical problems that normal classical computers won't solve). These researches have open up weak points in our present day classical computers that if eventually, the quantum computer is mass produced today, a lot of system will remain vulnerable to different attacks. Researches on quantum computer have proven that our present cryptographic system will not be capable of protecting data when the breakthrough is finally made. Digital communication will be adversely compromised. The integrity and confidentiality of users both online and offline will be jeopardized. This is the reason NIST highlighted the goal of post-quantum cryptographic system as building an enhanced or new cryptographic system that will secure both classical and quantum computers. They will seamlessly integrate with already existing network and communication protocols. (NIST, 2019).

II. QUANTUM COMPUTING

The marriage of quantum theory in physics with computer science is known as quantum computing (Mingsheng, 2010). In quantum computing, series of bits (qubits) are used to represent information. Unlike a normal bit, qubits can take the state of both 0 and 1 at the same time. When these qubits are extended, it gives rise to the great computational power of quantum computer.. (Horowitz, et.al, 2019).

Quantum computers cannot be likened to a group of parallel-arranged classical computers. Researchers have thought that an n-bit quantum computer can compute can

solve NP-complete problems faster due to the fact that qubits can occupy both states (0s and 1s) at the same time. A systematic transformation of qubits are performed on the intended information so that at the end of computation, the algorithm will not destroy the needed information, this makes a successful quantum algorithm. The implication is that no quantum algorithm that can solve all Np-Complete problems at the same time. Therefore, in other to use quantum algorithms to solve hard classical problems, one must exploit the specific structure of the problem at hand. (Zentachain, 2019).

Renty (2019) went ahead to highlight the algorithms that necessitated the need for improved quantum security on the present day primitive cryptography. To achieve this improvement, Post-quantum cryptography was born. The algorithms as highlighted by Renty (2019) are:

A. *Shor's Algorithm:*

Among the best-known and oldest quantum algorithms is Shor's algorithm which can effectively factorize integers and solve discrete logarithm problems. Come the day we're able to construct a quantum computer powerful enough to handle very large numbers using Shor's algorithm, all public-key cryptography based on these problems will be rendered immediately obsolete.

B. *Grover's algorithm:*

Grover's algorithm is another well-known quantum algorithm, which enables the inversion of functions. This algorithm can be applied to search effectively for items in an unordered list or unstructured database, something that can be likened to looking for a needle in a haystack. Grover's algorithm thus makes it possible to accelerate a search for a symmetric encryption key but does not call into question the principles of secret-key cryptography.

III. POST-QUANTUM CRYPTOGRAPHY AND TYPES

Post-quantum cryptography is the building of cryptosystems that can secure both classical computers and quantum computers should incase an intruder possess it. NIST initiated a process for standardizing post-quantum algorithms. The submissions included cryptosystems from the following types of cryptosystem. (NIST, 2019).

The major types of post-quantum cryptosystem are highlighted below;

A. *Lattice-Based Cryptosystem:*

Used for Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM) / Encryption, Due to the flexibility of Lattices, they are the most studied. They can be used for digital signature, key exchange and for fully homomorphic encryption. The underlying foundation for lattice cryptosystem is basic linear algebra notwithstanding the complex math involved for optimization and security proofs. The simple algebra is shown below.

$$\begin{aligned} a_{0,0}x_0 + a_{0,1}x_1 + \dots + a_{0,n}x_n &= y_0 \\ a_{1,0}x_0 + a_{1,1}x_1 + \dots + a_{1,n}x_n &= y_1 \\ &\vdots \\ a_{n,0}x_0 + a_{n,1}x_1 + \dots + a_{n,n}x_n &= y_n \end{aligned}$$

You can solve for x in a classic linear algebra problem that can be solved quickly using Gaussian elimination method. A mystery function is another way to solve this,

$$f_x(\mathbf{a}) = a_0x_0 + \dots + a_nx_n$$

Where "a" is a vector, we see the result of ax, and x is unknown. When this function is queried enough times we are able to learn f in a short amount of time (by solving the system of equations above). The linear algebra problem above can be modeled to a machine learning problem.

If a small noise is introduced to our algebraic function, add an error term e to the product of x and a then the whole thing is reduced to a modulo a (medium-sized) prime q. Then our noisy mystery function looks like

$$f_x(\mathbf{a}) = a_0x_0 + \dots + a_nx_n + \epsilon \pmod q$$

It is mathematically extremely difficult to learn this noisy function. Each loop in the Gaussian elimination method makes use of the noisy function, this increase the error term. The error term continues to increase as we continue in the loop until it swallows all information about the noisy function. This approach is what is called Learning With Errors (LWE) Problem in Lattice Cryptographic system. (Research Institute, 2019)

Learning With Errors problem (LWE) cryptosystems are call lattices because finding the shortest vector when proofing that LWE is NP-hard is called a lattice. Let's spare ourselves the scope of knowing what a lattice is mathematically. A lattice can be likened to a tiling of n-dimensional space in a nutshell.

Fig1: Diagram of a lattice (Research Institute, 2019)

Some of the lattice-based cryptosystems that mad the second round of NIST PQC standard are Kyber, Saber, FrodoKEM, Dilithium.

B. Code-Based Cryptosystem

Code-based cryptosystem is an encryption / key encapsulation mechanism (KEM). During communication, error in form of bit flips occurs. As the errors occur, the ability to withstand certain number of bit flips at the expense of message compactness is known as Error-correcting codes. For instance, 0 can be corrected to 000 and 1 to 111 for single bits. In this way, if a recipient gets 101, one will understand that 111 was actually sent. In like manner if the recipient gets 001, one will understand that 000 was originally sent by taking majority of the vote. This cannot actually work where the error happened on two bits such as 111 received as 001. The recipient will take the majority vote and arrive at 0 instead of 1. (Research Institute, 2019).

Linear code are one of the most-popular error-correcting codes and are represented by $k \times n$ matrices, where k stands for the length original message while n stand for the length of encoded message. It is generally difficult to decode messages without knowing the corresponding linear code. This hardness is what gives strength to the McEliece public key cryptosystem. (Research Institute, 2019). McEliece uses a conservative approach for key encapsulation and public key encryption. Large keys are trademarks of this crypto-algorithm and researcher trying to use small keys for this cryptosystem and not water the underlying security.. (Basu, Soni, Nabee, & Karri, n.d.)

C. Isogeny-based (Supersingular) Cryptosystem

Used for Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM) / Encryption. Isogeny-based cryptography uses the approach of walking through a sequence of elliptic curve instead of points on the elliptic curve.

Table 1: The evolution of Isogeny from Diffie-Hellman. (Costello, 2017)

	DH	ECDH	SIDH
Elements	integers g modulo prime	points P in curve group	curves E in isogeny class
Secrets	exponents x	scalars k	isogenies ϕ
computations	$g, x \mapsto g^x$	$k, P \mapsto [k]P$	$\phi, E \mapsto \phi(E)$
hard problem	given g, g^x find x	given $P, [k]P$ find k	given $E, \phi(E)$ find ϕ

In Supersingular Isogeny Diffie-Hellman (SIDH) scheme, secret keys are obtained from chain of isogenies and public keys are obtained from curves. For instance Alice and Bob combine this information, they acquire curves that are different, but have the same j -invariant. It's not so important for the purposes of cryptography what a j -invariant is, but rather that it is a number that can easily be computed by both Alice and Bob once they've completed the key exchange. The Isogeny-based cryptography uses only 330 bytes of public keys, the smallest among all post-quantum crypto-system competitors. They also possess perfect forward secrecy unlike other cryptosystems. (Research Institute, 2019)

D. Hash-Based Signature

Used for Digital signatures. The Merkle tree is used in the hash-based cryptosystem to reduce space. Hashes cannot be used to construct KEM or public key encryption schemes.

Hashes are mainly for signatures based schemes. Furthermore, they are extremely fast due to the fact that the cryptosystem requires only the computation of hash functions. This cryptosystem are extremely strong also. There has not been any confirmation that current widely used hash functions like SHA3 or BLAKE2 are vulnerable to attacks, hash-based crpto-system are secure. (Research Institute, 2019). Examples of these algorithms are SPHINCS+ and Picnic. Both are NIST second –round candidates.

E. Multivariate-Based Cryptosystem

Used for Digital signatures and Public-Key schemes. Multivariate cryptography used a set of polynomial known as multivariate polynomial (MVP) in several variables, of small degree over a small finite field. With the polynomial, verification of digital signature is very fast and short. It also has good performance and flexibility to its name. (Research Institute, 2019).

Some algorithms under this cryptosystem are Rainbow (Unbalanced Oil and Vinegar), MQDSS, LUOV etc. Rainbow is another multivariate signature scheme that is built as a quantum-resistant digital signature scheme. (Research Institute, 2019).

Table2: Complete list of post-quantum cryptographic algorithm (NIST Second Candidates)

S/No	PQC Algorithm	Type	Mechanism
1	BIKE	Code-Based	KEM
2	Classic McEliece	Code-Based	KEM
3	CRYSTALS-KYBER	Lattice-Based	KEM
4	FrodoKEM	Lattice-Based	KEM
5	HQC (Hamming Quasi-Cyclic)	Code-Based	KEM
6	LAC	Lattice-based	KEM
7	LEDAcrypt	Code-Based	KEM
8	NewHope	Ring-LWE	KEM
9	NTRU	Lattice-Based	KEM
10	NTRU Prime	Lattice-Based	KEM
11	NTS-KEM	Code-Based	KEM
12	ROLLO	Code-Based	KEM
13	Round5	Lattice-Based	KEM
14	Rank Quasi-Cyclic (RQC)	Code-Based	KEM
15	SABER	Lattice-Based	KEM

16	SIKE	Isogeny-based	KEM
17	Three Bears	Lattice-Based	KEM
18	CRYSTALS-DILITHIUM	Signatures Scheme	lattice-based signature
19	FALCON	Signatures Scheme	lattice-based signature
20	GeMSS	Signatures Scheme	Multivariate-based
21	LUOV	Signatures Scheme	Multivariate-based
22	MQDSS	Signatures Scheme	Multivariate-based
23	Picnic	Signatures Scheme	hash functions and block ciphers
24	qTESLA	Signatures Scheme	Code-based
26	Rainbow	Signatures Scheme	Multivariate-based
27	SPHINCS+	Signatures Scheme	Hash-based

IV. REVIEW OF SOME WORK DONE ON POST-QUANTUM CRYPTOGRAPHY

Rijneveld (2019) researched on various group of post-quantum cryptography algorithm. Firstly, He examined hash-based digital signature schemes, a thorough discussion of historical constructions, leading up to the recent XMSS, SPHINCS, and SPHINCS+ schemes. He further discussed its scheme design, and described several implementations, in particular on embedded platforms. a non-standard approach towards designing signature schemes based on the MQ problem was employed by him and MQDSS and SOFIA schemes were introduced. Secondly, Lattice-based KEM was also examined. Lattice-based key-encapsulation mechanisms with a focus on NTRU was optimized and implemented.

Gyurik (2018) in his research developed a new cryptography from the RSA primitive cryptographic algorithm. He worked a Post-Quantum RSA variation by Bernstein et al that was designed to withstand supposed quantum attacks better than RSA. He used large-scale quantum computers to investigate security of Post-Quantum RSA. He used element of relatively low multiplicative order to speed up Shor's algorithm then the unification of Lenstra's elliptic curve factorization method (ECM) and Shor's order-finding algorithm. Furthermore, he showcased how to use certain number of processors to speed up Shor's algorithm for classical or quantum operations in parallel.

Nejatollahi et al. (2019) demonstrated that latticed based cryptography algorithms can be implemented in softwares, hardwares and both softwares / hardwares. The lattice-based cryptography has schemes for Public key encryption, digital signature and key exchange. He highlighted the scheme for public key encryption as NTRU or LWE (variety of variants exists such as RLWE, MLWE, ILWE and MPLWE). He surveyed the implementation of this post-quantum cryptography (Lattice-based) algorithm on diversity of computing platforms.

Endignoux (2017) focused on hash based scheme using hash functions. His work relied on Preimage and collision resistance with regards to their security with hash function properties. Stateless hash-based signatures was efficiently improved and made Stateful. He further presented a cryptanalysis of the subset-resilience problem, showing new attacks and proposing fixes.

Yang (2019) asserted that multivariate scheme's security is based on the Problem MQ: where m multivariate quadratic polynomials $p(1), \dots, p(m)$, find a vector $w = (w_1, \dots, w_n)$ such that $p(1)(w) = \dots = p(m)(w) = 0$.

V. CONCLUSION

The latest advances in the technology of quantum computing have form a new challenge for modern cryptography. There are needs to find the novel ways of ensuring information security and its main properties -confidentiality, integrity, authentication and repudiation are achieved. More work should be done by scientists and researcher to unveil ways of improving these algorithms. We should make sure that tat post-quantum cryptosystem are ready before the mass production of large-scale quantum computers. With this is ready, our network and data will continue to be safe in the computing sphere.

VI. FUTURE RESEARCH AREAS

Post-Quantum Cryptography (PQC) is still in its infant stage and a lot of areas are begging for research and according to Ott & Peikert (2019), they include;

- A. PQC migration: Research that addresses the application of candidate algorithms to specific contexts and how migration within any given cryptographic usage domain can be realized in a secure way. Deploying this algorithms on several platforms like Web, Mobile IOT, VPN and Trusted computing architectures
- B. Cryptographic agility: Cryptographic agility addresses the important problem of future-proofing our global cryptographic infrastructure in a flexible and robust manner. Research are needed in the area of Implementation Agility, Compliance Agility, Security Strength Agility etc
- C. Other Areas are in Policy making, Process and people. Areas of emerging trends like Blockchain PQC, Password-authenticated Key Agreement (PAKE), Secure Multi-Party Computation (MPC) and more

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